

A Survey on Agri-Crisis in India Based on Engineering Aspects

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Abstract

For a large agrarian economy like India's that is predominantly dependant on Agriculture as their principal source of livelihood, few can hardly believe it's acute crisis in this very sector in the recent days. After Green Revolution, India, which was dependant on the imports of food grains to feed its population, has turned into a self sufficient economy with high growth rates in Agriculture. But the high growth rate was not long lasting and had various adverse effects rendering the Agriculture sector in a deep crisis. So, it is the high time to save Agriculture, to save India solving the root causes. In this paper we have unveiled few causes from engineering perspective which are also responsible for this crisis, but not considered yet. An effort has also been given towards solving these problems employing modern and innovative methodologies.

Keywords: *EM radiation, RF shielding, Global Chemical Pollution (GCP), Information and Communication Technology (ICT).*

1 Introduction

“Is it a sin to be a farmer?” – These words are really haunting as Agriculture in India, which has a significant history, is now no more profitable economic activity in comparison to other enterprises. Though it is hard to believe but the tragic face of India's agrarian crisis is exposed in the increasing number of farmer suicides. Over the past ten years, more than 200,000 farmers have committed suicide, not just in the rural areas of India, but in the allegedly prosperous agricultural zones of India like Punjab- ‘The Bread-basket of India’ and Burdwan- ‘The Rice bowl of east’. These thousands suicides are only the tip of the ice-berg of increasing deprivation. In this paper we have tried to find out the root causes of this acute Agricultural crisis in India in engineering perspective.

2 Root Causes of Agrarian Crisis in India and Their Probable Solutions

It is argued that the consequence of Agricultural crisis in India is very vast and likely to hit all other sectors and the national economy in several ways and therefore this Agri-crisis is a crisis of the country as a whole. The related factors, responsible for this crisis include (a) dependence on

rain fall and climate, (b) liberal import of agricultural products, (c) reduction in agricultural subsidies, (d) repeated crop failure, (e) lack of easy credit to agriculture, (f) dependence on private money lenders, and last but not the least (g) conversion of farm land for alternative uses.

The above mentioned causes are discussed several times. So, in this paper, we have put forward our sincere effort to find out other unveiled causes which are also responsible for this vast crisis. As well, we have tried to come out with their probable solutions towards solving this crisis.

2.1 Improper use of world-wide used Wireless Communication Technology

Wireless Communication is the buzz technology now- a- days, which helps in exchanging information world wide swiftly and smartly. But, most of us are least bothered about the invisible Electro Magnetic (EM) radiation of mobile towers, which silently affects birds, bees, animals, human beings and plants severely. It has been found that a GSM900 base station antenna transmits in the frequency range of 935-960 MHz (25MHz) which is divided into 200 sub-bands of 1.2 MHz each and are allotted to several operators. Each operator may transmit 50-100 watt of power and there may be 3-4 operators on the same roof top or tower, thereby total transmitted power may be 200-400 watt. Isotropic antennas are usually preferred over directional antennas for giving coverage to a region. Isotropic antennas radiate equally in all directions and its radiated power density P_d at a distance R from a transmitter is measured as

$$P_d = \frac{P_t \times G_t}{4 \pi R^2} \text{ watt/m}^2 \quad (1)$$

Where P_t is transmitter power (in watt), G_t is gain of transmitting antenna and R is the distance from the transmitting antenna (in meters). Again the peak transmitted power output of a system is described by the parameters known as Effective Radiated Power (ERP) or Effective Isotropically Radiated Power (EIRP) as follows

$$\text{EIRP} = P_t \times G_t \quad (2)$$

With the definition of EIRP, equation (1) can be modified as described in equation (3) below

$$P_d = \frac{\text{EIRP}}{4 \pi R^2} \quad (3)$$

Now, Effective (or Equivalent) Radiated Power is mathematically written as

$$\text{ERP} = \frac{P_t \times G_t}{1.64} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or, ERP} = \frac{\text{EIRP}}{1.64} \quad (5)$$

Like human body, plants also consist of liquid, which gets heated up due to the absorption of this EM radiation, affecting the overall growth of the agricultural crops and plants. A reduction in wheat and corn yield in the fields near high EM radiation has also been reported (shown in Figure1.a). Trees located inside the *main lobe (beam)* of EM radiation field (shown in Figure1.b), look sad and feeble, have dried tops, show slow growth and high susceptibility to illness. The micro organisms present in the soil may be killed too, due to the heat generated by the EM radiation, which in turn disturbs the ecological cycle.

Figure 1.a: Change In EM radiated power density with the change in distance from the transmitting antenna.

Figure 1.b: Main lobe of the transmitting antenna is the major harmful region for most of the plants.

RF shielding the practice of reducing the electromagnetic field in a space by blocking the field with barriers made of conductive or magnetic materials. It is typically applied to enclosures to isolate EM radiation from the 'outside world', and to cables to isolate wires from the environment through which the cable runs. Though the employment of the technology mentioned here, is quite expensive, it is expected to save us, our environment and so the Agricultural crops too.

In spite of the risk associated with the mobile phones, now a days we all are habituated to use it any where any time in our daily life. So it is advisable to use this modern tool effectively in agriculture sector also. Different Mobile applications may take to help agricultural sector. Mobile agricultural applications (shown in Table.1), in this context, may (1) educate and raise awareness, (2) distribute price information, (3) collect data, and (4) track pests and diseases.

Table.1: Roles of Mobile Phones in Agriculture

Objective	Procedure
Education and awareness	Information provided via mobile phones to farmers and extension agents about good practices, improved crop varieties, and pest or disease management.
Commodity prices and market information	Prices in regional markets to inform decision making throughout the entire Agricultural process.
Data collection	Applications that collect data from large geographic regions.
Pest and disease outbreak warning and tracking	Send and receive data on outbreaks.

2.2 Improper utilization of the most powerful Information Technology in Agriculture

The world is becoming a global village today, as the difference between the nations has been reduced with the help of Information Technology (IT). But unfortunately this technology is not yet been employed efficiently in the sector of Agriculture in India.

Information of the required quality always has the potential of improving efficiency in every sphere of life and so in Agriculture. Utilizing IT, agrarian research institutes and many other organizations may provide solutions to the problems faced by the farmers, in a cost-effective manner. Exclusive TV channels are to be there in each state dedicated to agriculture, to enable the farmers more equipped with the modern and expert technology.

“Evening Red and morning Gray, Will set the traveler on his way”, from this popular passed-through generations folk songs, it is very clear that still the rural people rely on the interpretation of cloud colors, animal behaviors, flowing of certain plants, and many other observations as they are not provided with the weather forecasting information timely. Consequently, the agrarian communities have to face a lot of problems including crop-damage.

Advanced climate prediction technology in combination with IT may be employed to communicate the farmers about year-to-year variability of monsoon behavior and its advance measures to manage risk at least to some degree.

The potential of IT lies in bringing about an overall qualitative improvement in life by empowering people. So, not only the farmers, young people are to be trained too. Tamilnadu Agriculture University (TAU) has pioneered in this approach introducing a unique course- B.Tech in ‘Agriculture-IT’.

2.3 Chem-Biotechnology is mostly unutilized in Agrarian Sector

Although the Green Revolution increased grain production and enabled India for example to become self-sufficient with a surplus for export and donation, it has depleted natural resources base such as a steep fall in ground water table, impaired water quality, created deficiency of micro-nutrients in the soil deteriorating soil health. Too much use of fertilizers such as nitrogen has had adverse environmental effects. It has been shown that some of the nitrogen leaves fields with runoffs, damaging rivers, wetlands, estuaries and seas through the depletion of oxygen. Biodiversity has also been adversely affected including the disappearance of some types of fishery resources. Too much irrigation water has also been reported as environmentally harmful. Over-watering has had negative impact on soil composition with an increase in salinity and a reduction in soil productivity. There is also the ecological disturbance from spraying of the DDT (dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane). It has been shown that even relatively non-volatile pesticides such as DDT evaporate into the atmosphere quite rapidly, particularly in hot climates, and can be transported over long distances, contributing to what has been known as **Global Chemical Pollution (GCP)**.

In order to overcome these adverse effects of Green Revolution, further researches are badly needed in the field of Chemical engineering, Agriculture Science and Bio technology. Even Chem-Biotechnology, the combination disciplines are warmly welcome today. Chemical engineering has played a leading role in improving production in the field of agriculture. Additionally, modern biotechnology holds considerable promise to meet the challenges in agriculture production.

Combination of Chem-Biotechnology and Agriculture Engineering can (a) develop high yielding and nutritious crop varieties, (b) improve resistance to plant diseases, (c) reduce the need for fertilizer as well as expensive chemical products, which were key components of green revolution, (d) introduce such qualities of crops as **disease-resistant** and increased **drought-tolerant** by using the genes of naturally drought-resistant plants to plants which need much water.

These modern technologies are expected to overcome the crisis of Agriculture in India and additionally, the eco friendly technology minimizes farm worker exposure to hazardous products.

2.4 Roadmap to Enhance Existing Agriculture Technology

So far we have discussed few root causes and their probable solutions towards agriculture sector separately. In this section an effort has been given to enhance the existing agriculture technology by combining several technologies together. The concept has been proposed with the help of the Figure2, shown below. Bio-Technology (BT), Environment Technology (ET), existing Cultivation

Technology (CT), Management Technology(MT) are brilliantly combined with the modern Information and Communication Technology (ICT), which is still under serious research, to revolutionize the existing agriculture sector. And feedback from the knowledgebase boosts up the technology day by day to pave the path for the Advanced Agriculture Technology.

Figure2: Roadmap to achieve Advanced Agriculture Technology

3 Conclusion

In India, Agriculture plays a dominant role in sustaining the livelihood of more than 70% of India's population. Even industrial and services sectors are invariably entangled with the fortunes of agriculture due to various intricate forward and backward linkages. But, there have been ominous signs which showed that the Indian agriculture is in crisis. One of them is unending chain of suicides by farmers in different parts of the country. As solution different "packages" have been proposed, but they are very superficial. In this paper we have emphasized on some unveiled causes of this vast crisis. We have also thought about some innovative methods towards solving this problem helping the poor farmers and rural economy. Developed India is possible with the attainment of growing, advancement of manufacturing and services sector. But prosperous India is possible only with healthy agricultural sector. The pride and confidence in farmers and farming needs to be restored. This alone can help agriculture grow like never before and we can highlight India's image as "Shining India", "Incredible India" in the international platform.

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